

Integrating Information Ethics in Library and Information Science Curricula in Zimbabwe: Country Report presented at a Teaching Information Ethics in Africa Conference held at the University of Botswana, 6 – 7 September 2010 by Lawton Hikwa¹

Introduction

The demand and drive for countries of the developing world to transform into knowledge economies cannot be overemphasised. This has largely been influenced by the obvious desire for an information society in which information is considered an economic resource. Within such a society, it is almost generally agreed and understood that the creation, distribution, diffusion, use and manipulation of information is a major economic, political and cultural activity. Also central to an information society is the role of information and communications technologies (ICTs) in driving the production and economic agenda of such a society. From these perspectives, emerge the need to consider ethical creation, distribution, diffusion, use and manipulation of information.

This paper provides a historical overview of LIS education in Zimbabwe and how the teaching of information ethics is carried out.

Library and Information Science (LIS) Education in Zimbabwe: an Historical Overview and Situational Analysis

LIS education in Zimbabwe was considerably slower in development than in neighbouring South Africa, Botswana and Zambia as a result of the powerful influence of the British pattern and background in the first phase of local training of librarians, subsequently yielding to American influence (Hikwa, 1990: 20). Requirements born of Zimbabwean conditions gave the course of development a character of its own. Nevertheless, the evolution of LIS education followed the general pattern and went through very much the same phases as elsewhere.

In the period of the British occupation of Zimbabwe all the institutions that were established followed the British pattern. Systems of education, government services and economic structures all bore British character. It was therefore natural for the Zimbabwean library system to incorporate in its development British methods, techniques and concepts (ibid).

With the advent of the 19th century, libraries developed extensively, particularly in the more populous settler centres (later developing into urban settlements), creating an urgent demand for librarians. This need was met by the importation of British librarians, of whom some had served an apprenticeship in libraries at home and others had successfully taken the examinations of the Library Association (ibid., p. 21). Decades later, the influx of British librarians gave a definite shape and design to the organisation of librarianship in Zimbabwe.

It is understandable that the importation of British librarians should have given Zimbabwean librarianship a manifestly British character. Training of librarians, or more appropriately, library assistants, scant as it was from early beginnings, bore the British stamp. Examinations were set and marked in London and graduates awarded the City and Guilds of London Institute Certificates in library assistance (Wise, M. (ed), 1985: 52). In 1970, the report of the Greenfield Commission stated categorically that the education of librarians was indispensable of library services; "... that correspondence courses did not meet the requisite needs since education for librarianship should be in line with the specific requirements of the country; that a (Zimbabwean) library or university college should initiate such a form of education by way of vacation courses; and that the education for librarianship should eventually be conducted by a university or college, which might avail itself of British correspondence courses in the initial stage." (Greenfield, C. [Chairman], 1970: 42).

Following recommendations passed by the Greenfield Commission, a City and Guilds of London Institute course was started at the Harare Polytechnic and later at the Technical College, Bulawayo (*Ibid*). Students were taught by volunteer, professional librarians on a day-release basis. The course was studied over one year and has since 1985 been replaced by the National Certificate in Library and Information Work.

In 1985 a Department of Library and Information Science was established at the Harare Polytechnic (Thorpe, D.M., 1988: 4). Over the years, LIS education has expanded to other Polytechnics and eventually the National University of Science and Technology. At Polytechnic level, LIS education is in three stages:

- a) National Certificate in Library and Information Science, a one year long course that prepares candidates for basic assistance in library and information practice.
- b) National Diploma in Library and Information Science, a two-year long course that prepares candidates for paraprofessional engagement in library and information practice.
- c) Higher National Diploma in Library and Information Science, a year-long course that prepares candidates for all kinds of semi-professional work in library and information practice.

At university level, studies are taken for the Bachelor of Science Honours Degree in Library and Information Science, a four-year long programme that prepares candidates for professional

work in library and information practice.¹ Further, candidates may pursue studies in the same at Master's level. Higher degrees by research are also offered up to postdoctoral level. Appended at the end of this paper are outlines of each of the programmes stated above for further perusal and contextualisation of the discussion that follow.

Information Ethics: the Zimbabwean Context

In the context of Zimbabwe, information ethics is understood to be that field which investigates ethical issues emerging from the application of ICTs in information delivery. Such issues may include moral issues surrounding privacy, censorship, moral agency, behaviour in the cybersphere, information life-cycle, ownership of information, copyright, legal issues, access to information, balance in collection development, codes of ethics, problem users, users with special needs, the digital divide, intellectual property rights, nonmaleficence (do not harm), etc. The whole idea of thinking ethically around information is influenced by the desire to develop and sustain an information society.

Some of the driving characteristics of an information society include an ethical framework that makes it possible for fair, equitable and responsible practices within the LIS field. The emergence of ICT has affected fundamental rights related to copyright protection, intellectual freedom, accountability and security. In other words, "the Information Society should be subject to universally held values and promote the common good and to prevent abusive use of ICTs." (IFLA, 2007: 27). In this context, ethical dimensions of the Information Society include taking "steps to promote respect for peace and to uphold the fundamental values for freedom, equality, solidarity, tolerance, shared responsibility, and respect for nature" (*Ibid*). In addition, stakeholders are supposed to increase their awareness of the ethical dimension of their use of ICTs. "All actors in the Information Society should promote the common good, protect privacy and personal data and take appropriate actions and preventive measures, as determined by law, against abusive use of ICTs such as illegal and other acts motivated by racism, racial discrimination, xenophobia, and related intolerance, hatred, violence, all forms of child abuse, including paedophilia and child pornography, and trafficking in, and exploitation of, human beings" (*Ibid*: 28).

From the above, it becomes clear that LIS curricula can no longer afford treating information ethics as a piece meal facet of their mandate, but rather as an emerging crosscutting discipline deserving to be researched upon.

¹ The National University of Science and Technology was the first (and still is the only) institution to offer degree studies in LIS in 2001 at the recommendation of a Commission of Inquiry into the establishment of a second university campus in Zimbabwe.

Schools of LIS in Zimbabwe do not have specific courses devoted specifically or wholly to information ethics. Information ethics tends to be taught in the context of broader course modules. The obtaining situation regarding the teaching of information ethics can be summarised thus:

Course Level	Course Modules with Ethical Elements	Remarks
National Certificate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Libraries in Society • Reference and Information Services • Introduction to Information Technology 	<p>These modules do not explicitly mention information ethics, but have dimensions of it. For example, Libraries and Society includes though briefly, topics about censorship, access, copyright, etc. There is also emphasis on the accuracy of information sources and responsible use of information technology, particularly the Internet.</p>
National Diploma	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collection Development and Reference Services • Data Communication in Libraries • Production and Publishing 	<p>There is no explicit mention of information ethics; however, aspects of it are inferred in all these modules. Examples are equitable selection and collection development, accuracy of data, copyright issues, etc.</p>
National Higher Diploma	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Libraries and Society • Database Management 	<p>The modules include the sociology of information and accuracy of data both of which have ethical dimensions.</p>
Bachelor of Science Honours Degree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to Information Technology • Collection Development and Management • Information Sources and Services • Information Retrieval Systems • Application of Information Technology Tools and in Libraries and Archives • Information and Society 	<p>The modules include the importance of using licensed software, equitable collection development and management, accuracy of information sources, legal issues, copyright issues and responsible use of ICTs, including the Internet. A comparison of world library and information systems is also studied in depth and includes some ethical issues such as censorship, copyright, etc.</p>

Course Level	Course Modules with Ethical Elements	Remarks
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online Information Retrieval • Legal and Professional Issues • Production and Publishing of Information Media • Design and Realisation of Internet Information • Comparative Librarianship 	
Master of Science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced Information Technology Applications • Contemporary Issues in Library and Information Management • Information and Communication Theory • Indigenous Knowledge Systems • Information Policy Studies • Sociology of Information 	All these modules have some inference on information ethics, particularly about accuracy of data, use of the Internet, access to information, privacy, policy, intellectual property rights and the political economy of information. Nevertheless, information ethics is not explicitly mentioned.
Higher Degrees	These are by research	Candidates are free to research on any topic of their choice. So far, there is very limited research at this level that is explicitly on and/or about information ethics

Conclusion

From the scenario reported above, there is an urgent need to either integrate information ethics in the current LIS curricula in Zimbabwe or draw up a completely new course on the same that is guided by international trends and best practices. Such a stand-alone course could address a broader variety of topics: computer crime, copyright, privacy, software reliability,

artificial intelligence, e-governance, e-commerce, etc. (Froehlich, T., 2004). Further the course might want to look at ethics and the law including ethical principles, ethical decision-making, ethics codes, and codes of conduct, community standards and legal issues.

Better still, there could be consideration of teaching information ethics from a global perspective. In fact, IFLA already has a suggested outline for the same (Smith, M.M., 2002). In Summary, this outlines the consideration of five key areas:

- Foundations: History, Philosophy and Public Policy (with suggested trajectories for analysis)
- Major Issues: Access, Ownership, Privacy, Security and Community
- Professional Issues and Ethics in the Global Context: Preparing for the Future
- The Ethical Challenges of the Global Information Infrastructure
- The Future of Global Information Ethics

The above suggestions are not absolute, but can be discussed and tailor-made for use within several and different contexts.

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Appendix I

Bulawayo, Harare and Joshua Mqabuko Nkomo Polytechnics

National Certificate in Library and Information Science

Year 1

Organisation of knowledge

Libraries in society

Reference and information services

Library operations and procedures

Communication

Introduction to information technology

National strategic studies

Entrepreneurship studies

National Diploma in Library and Information Science

Year 2

Records management

Cataloguing I

Classification I

Collection development and reference services I

Library management I

Data communications in Libraries

Year 3

Industrial attachment

Year 4

Cataloguing II

Classification II

Collection development and reference services II

Library management II

Production and publishing

Research methods and statistics

Higher National Diploma in Library and Information Science

Year 5

Human resources management

Records and archives administration

Libraries and society

Database management

Research project

Appendix II

BSc (Hons) Library and Information Science Courses offered at NUST

Year I

Semester I

ILI 1101	Organisation of knowledge I
ILI 1103	Introduction to information technology
ILI 1104	Collection development and management
ILI 1105	Communication skills
ILI 1106	Automation of Library processes

Semester II

ILI 1202	Information Sources and Services
ILI 1203	Information Retrieval Systems
ILI 1204	Applications of Information Technology Tools in Libraries and Archives
ILI 1205	Organisation of Knowledge II
ILI 1206	CDS/ISIS Computerised Documentation Systems/ Information Systems for Information Services
ILI 1207	Information and Society

Year 2

Semester I

ILI 2102	Online information retrieval
ILI 2103	Legal and professional issues
ILI 2104	Production and publishing of information media I
ILI 2106	Indexing and abstracting
ILI 2107	Information management in the health sciences

Semester II

ILI 2201	Database Applications in Archives, Libraries and Publishing
ILI 2202	Production and Publishing of Information Media II
ILI 2203	Research Methods and Statistics
ILI 2204	Archival and Library Information Systems Management
ILI 2205	Design and Realisation of Internet Information in Libraries and Archives
ILI 2206	Management of Libraries

Year 3

Industrial attachment

Year 4

Semester I

ILI 4102	Marketing of information products and services
ILI 4106	Comparative librarianship
ILI 4107	Publishing management: advanced theory and practice
ILI 4005	Research Seminars

Semester II

ILI 4201	Academic Libraries
ILI 4202	Public Libraries
ILI 4205	Children's Libraries
ILI 4207	School Library Media Centres
ILI 4209	Special Libraries

Appendix III

MSc Library and Information Science Courses offered at NUST

Core courses

ILI 5101	Advanced Information Technology Applications
ILI 5102	Research Methods and Data Analysis Techniques
ILI 5103	Contemporary Issues in Library and Information Management
ILI 5104	Information and Communication Theory
ILI 5105	Indigenous Knowledge Systems
ILI 5000	Research seminars

Elective Courses (3)

ILI 5106	Information Policy Studies
ILI 5107	Management Information Systems
ILI 5108	Specialised Information Systems in Agriculture, Health, Development Studies, etc
ILI 5109	Advanced Records Management
ILI 5110	Advanced Archives Management
ILI 5111	Sociology of Information

Qualifying Research Project

ILI 5000	Dissertation
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